

THE COMPARISON OF SOMATIC LEXICON'S PECULIAR FEATURES IN THE SYSTEM OF NON-RELATED LANGUAGES

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the studying the characteristics of the somatic lexicon in a system of non-related languages. The scientific article carried out an analysis of the somatic lexicon's expression of human or animal body organs and their role in the understanding of the human being in the world, their characteristic features in themselves.

Keywords: Lexicon, somatic lexicon, somatism, somatic vocabulary, polysemic.

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СРАВНЕНИЕ ХАРАКТЕРНЫХ ОСОБЕННОСТЕЙ СОМАТИЧЕСКОЙ ЛЕКСИКИ В СИСТЕМЕ НЕРОДСТВЕННЫХ ЯЗЫКОВ

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Abstract: Данная статья представляет собой сравнение особенностей соматического лексикона в системе неродственных языков. В научной статье был проведен анализ того, как соматический лексикон представляет органы тела человека или животного и их роль в понимании человеком Вселенной, их уникальных особенностей.

Keywords: лексика, соматическая лексика, соматизм, соматическая лексика, полисемия..

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SOMATIK LEKSIKONNING O`ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARINI QARINDOSH BO'LMAGAN TILLAR TIZIMIDA TAQQOSLASH

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Abstract: Ushbu maqola somatik leksikonning o`ziga xos xususiyatlarini qarindosh bo'lmagan tillar tizimida taqqoslashdan iborat. Ilmiy maqolada somatik leksikaning inson yoki hayvon tana a`zolarini ifodalashi va ularning insonni olamni anglashidagi o`rni, ularning o`zida xos xususiyatlari haqida tahlil olib borilgan..

Keywords: Leksika, somatik leksika, somatizm, somatik lug`at, polisemiya

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Introduction. It is known that the word *lexicon* is derived from the Greek word, which means "word-specific", "dictionary". The *lexicon* is the *sum of all the words and phrases* that make up a language, which constitutes the vocabulary of a language. The lexicon of language has the property of a great change. This can be observed in such a way that some words lose their meaning and are completely unused or form a new meaning, as well as the penetration of words that do not exist in the language into the language. The lexicon of language becomes rich in connection with the development progress of society. In particular, achievements in science and technology also lead to the emergence of new words in the lexical layer of the language,

Literature analysis. Now, with the main focus on the somatic lexicon, when it is called somatic lexicon, the words that represent the human or animal body organs present in the language are understood. *Somatic lexicon* exists in all languages and belongs to the universal lexical layer of languages. The term somatism comes from the Greek word "soma", which means body. Somatisms are words that represent human or animal body organs. The introduction of the terms somatic lexicon and somatism in linguistics, Estonian language researcher F.O.Vakk is associated with the name. In his opinion: "Somatisms belong to one of the oldest layers of phraseology and constitute the most used part of any vocabulary." It divides somatisms into the following types: 1) those that describe a person; 2) those that describe a person and an animal; 3) those that describe an animal.

Analyzes and results. F.O.Vakk notes: somatisms cover not only the organs of reproaches, but also the name of the body fluids, such as nerves, bones, muscles that are inextricably linked with them, even if they do not belong to the order of the body organs, as well as vocabulary formed as a result of gestures.

A person perceives himself, the perception of the surrounding world through his own scolding members, and also feels other objects and objects in the universe through his body organs, compares them with them.

According to T.N. Chayko: the constant human eye presence of somatisms has made them a benchmark that serves to compare other things. Somatisms are actively used to form meaning through metaphors, and on its basis is observation of the behavior of Man and animals. He sees man as a source of comparison of his scorn members, the tasks they perform, in his understanding of the universe, in the reflection of objects and objects in it in his mind.

F.O.Gakk says: "Man is egocentric; he sees in himself the center of the universe and reflects the universe in his image.

Somatisms, that is, in addition to dividing body organs into internal and external organs, linguist scientists studied them in several groups.

Somatic dictionaries depending on the nature of the nomination object, Yu.R.Mugu in his scientific work M.A. Kochevatkin states that the following groups are divided by:

1. Samonymic dictionary. Being the largest part of somatic vocabulary, they serve to define human body parts and places.

2. Osteonymic dictionary. Osteonymic vocabulary is used to designate the bones of the human body.

3. Splanchnonymic dictionary. Splanchnonymic vocabulary internal organs of the human body. used for naming

4. Angionomic vocabulary. To name the circulatory systems of the human body, an angionomic dictionary is used.

5. Sensory vocabulary. Sensory vocabulary serves to designate the sensory organs of a person.

6. A dictionary denoting diseases and manifestations of a person's organism.

Somatic vocabulary (Greek "soma" - "body" one of the universal lexical groups in any language is the most common object of research in comparative, historical, linguo-culturological works of domestic and foreign linguists, usually it is the lexical-thematic system of any language that first distinguishes vocabulary. Somatisms are nouns that have the original meaning of parts of the body of a person or animal. Somatisms that is, if we give an example of words denoting body organs: *bosh/head, ko`z/eyes, quloq/ears, sovh/hair, og`iz/mouth, burun/nose, til/tongue* or words such as *head, eye, ear, hair, mouth, tongue, tongue*, we realize that the noun belongs to the word category. One of their distinctive features is their inclusion in the order of this word category.

Another important feature of the somatic lexicon is the multiple observation of the phenomenon of polysemy in it. When we compare the words "bosh/head" in Uzbek and "head" in English, their possession of many meanings does not attract attention. In this, these words can be used in both languages with other meanings, such as the mind, leader or boss, the upper part of something, again, in addition to the upper part of the human or animal body. Of course, this is their mutual similarity.

Conclusions. Somatic lexicon is words that are expressed by human or animal body organs. In somatic lexicons, scientists also introduce words that depend on the members of the reproach, fluid in the human body, which is, blood, muscles, bones, etc.

In order for a person to reflect in his mind the world that surrounds him, what is in him perceives objects with his body organs and learns by comparing them with them.

A characteristic feature of the somatic lexical layer is the fact that these words belong to the noun word category.

The somatic lexicon is also characteristic of the phenomenon of polysemy, which also expresses other meanings.

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